

FRM4DOAS-BO_Phase2_D4

WPs 2250-2251: “DOAS-BO: Towards a new FRM4DOAS-compliant site - Phase 2”

[D-4] Report on the inter-comparison results between MAX-DOAS Tropospheric VCDs and S-5P TROPOMI “corrected” NO₂ Tropospheric VCDs

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1. List of Acronyms

AK	Averaging Kernels
AOD	Aerosol Optical Depth
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
DOAS	Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy
FRM4DOAS	Fiducial Reference Measurements for DOAS
KNMI	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut
ISAC	Istituto delle Scienze dell'Atmosfera e del Clima
MAX-DOAS	Multi-AXis DOAS
SCD	Slant Column Densities
SPC	San Pietro Capofiume
STD	Standard Deviation
SZA	Solar Zenith Angle
S-5p	Sentinel-5 precursor
TROPOMI	TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument
UV	Ultra-Violet
VCD	Vertical Column Density
VIS	Visible

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2. Introduction

This document is the report of the activities performed in the frame of the project “WPs-2250-2251: DOAS-BO: Towards a new FRM4DOAS-compliant site - Phase 2”. Here we report the outcomes of the comparisons between SPC MAX-DOAS NO₂ Tropospheric VCDs and S-5p TROPOMI Tropospheric VCDs modified using MAX-DOAS profiles for the a-priori satellite corrections.

3. TROPOMI NO₂ Tropospheric VCDs correction to account for a-priori NO₂ profiles

Tropospheric NO₂ VCDs are retrieved from S-5p TROPOMI measurements using the retrieval algorithm developed at KNMI [R1]. The algorithm is divided into three main steps. First, they retrieve the total NO₂ slant column density. Then, the total column is separated into stratospheric and tropospheric SCDs. In the last step, the tropospheric and stratospheric NO₂ SCDs are converted to VCDs. For this last purpose, vertically resolved AMFs are calculated using NO₂ vertical profiles from the TM5-MP model [R2]. The TM5-MP model NO₂ profiles are reported at 1x1 latitude longitude degree resolution. This resolution is relatively coarse, and some structures can be smeared out. Several studies (e.g., [R3]) show that recalculating the S-5p TROPOMI columns using daily median MAX-DOAS profiles as a-priori improves the agreement between satellite and MAX-DOAS data. Using more realistic a-priori NO₂ profiles in S-5p TROPOMI retrievals thus, increase the accuracy of satellite retrieved tropospheric NO₂.

In [R6], we compared the retrieved SPC MAX-DOAS NO₂ tropospheric VCDs with standard S-5p TROPOMI products. A negative bias was found, with S-5p TROPOMI underestimating tropospheric VCDs. In this report, we repeat the comparison but “correcting” the S-5p TROPOMI VCDs for the a-priori profiles. Here we use the approach described in S-5p user manual section 8.8 [R2] to obtain TROPOMI Tropospheric VCDs corrected for the a-priori profile:

$$VCD_{SAT-TROPOSPHERIC}^{MAXDOAS-pro} = VCD_{SAT-TROPOSPHERIC} \frac{\sum_i c_i}{\sum_i AK_i^{TROPOSPHERIC} c_i} \quad [1]$$

With

$$AK^{TROPOSPHERIC} = \frac{AMF}{AMF^{TROPOSPHERIC}} \text{ below tropopause level} \quad [2]$$
$$AK^{TROPOSPHERIC} = 0 \text{ above tropopause level}$$

The S-5p TROPOMI L2 files include all the information needed for the calculation of the correction: the AK and the total, and the tropospheric AMF. To calculate the corrections, we also need the values of the MAX-DOAS NO₂ retrieved profiles interpolated at AK altitude levels. In this case, we use the NO₂ profiles obtained by averaging the MAX-DOAS profiles within an interval of +/- 15 minutes from S-5p TROPOMI overpasses and including profiles that do not present negative values at any altitude level. Data from the three MAX-DOAS azimuth directions (135°, 250° and 315°, Fig. 1) are used together for the averaging. The decision to use average profiles has been taken in order to reduce the impact of possible oscillations in MAX-DOAS retrieved profiles.

4. Comparison of NO₂ Tropospheric VCDs from SkySpec-2D and TROPOMI data

To ease the comparison with the S-5p TROPOMI corrected VCDs, we report the results of the SkySpec-2D vs S-5p TROPOMI inter-comparison extending the ones reported in [R6]. We exploit the results obtained when applying the DEAP code to more than 1 year of clear sky MAX-DOAS measurements from 1st October 2021 to 31st December 2022. We briefly recall the MAX-DOAS acquisition strategy used at SPC: the atmospheric spectra start to be acquired every morning when the SZA becomes lower than 94° (the sun is 4° below the horizon). In the beginning, the SkySpec-2D starts to acquire only zenith-sky spectra. When the SZA is lower than 85°, SkySpec-2D performs MAX-DOAS measurements. During MAX-DOAS acquisitions, SkySpec-2D measures in three different azimuth directions: 120°, 225° and 300° from 1st October 2021 to 23rd March 2022, and 135°, 250° and 315° afterwards (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Different views from SkySpec-2D in the three azimuth directions (135°, 250° and 315° after the 23rd of March 2022) adopted during MAX-DOAS measurements.

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Figure 2: Scatter plots of NO₂ tropospheric VCDs retrieved from SkySpec-2D MAX-DOAS measurements and coincident (see text for details) S-5p TROPOMI data at the “Giorgio Fea” observatory at San Pietro Capofiume (Bologna, Italy).

Figure 3: Timeseries of NO₂ tropospheric VCDs retrieved from SkySpec-2D MAX-DOAS measurements and coincident (see text for details) TROPOMI data at the “Giorgio Fea” observatory at San Pietro Capofiume (Bologna, Italy).

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In Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, we report the results of the comparison of NO₂ Tropospheric VCDs obtained from SkySpec-2D scans at 135, 250 and 313 azimuth degrees and S-5p TROPOMI data in coincidence. For the comparison, we considered S-5p TROPOMI data in a radius of 5 km around SPC and MAX-DOAS data within +/- 15 minutes from S-5p TROPOMI overpass. Only S-5p TROPOMI NO₂ data with quality above 0.75 are used in the comparison.

The mean bias, calculated as S-5p TROPOMI minus SkySpec-2D NO₂ VCDs, is negative: about from -0.9×10^{14} mol/cm². This result is largely expected considering S-5p TROPOMI's previous and routine validations that highlight as S-5p TROPOMI tends to underestimate NO₂ Tropospheric VCDs in polluted regions due to the use of modelled TM5 NO₂ a-priori profiles [R3, R6]. The slope is 0.69, while the correlation is 0.88.

In [R6], we show the results obtained when we use as a-priori information for aerosol extinction the shape from ALC data (and also AOD from CIMEL 318-T) over a few days. These results are only slightly different from (slightly better than) the ones obtained when no a-priori aerosol information from collocated measurement is used. For the extensive comparison reported here, we thus prefer to use the whole year of NO₂ tropospheric columns retrieved with no a-priori information from ALC and CIMEL 318-T. Tropospheric NO₂ VCDs retrieved with the use of a-priori aerosol measurement information will be used only as test cases.

5. Comparison of NO₂ Tropospheric VCDs from SkySpec-2D and S-5p TROPOMI data corrected using a-priori NO₂ profiles for SkySpec-2D

The S-5p TROPOMI Tropospheric VCDs have been corrected using Eq. [1]. The results of the scatter plots reported in Fig. 2 when using corrected S-5p TROPOMI VCDs are shown in Fig. 4, and the corresponding time series are shown in Fig. 5. The bias S-5p TROPOMI - SkySpec-2D is now slightly positive (about 2.7×10^{14} mol/cm²) and reduced with respect to the uncorrected case. The slope increases from 0.69 to 0.77, while the correlation now goes from 0.88 to 0.86. In general, the correction has the expected effect of enhancing TROPOMI VCDs.

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Figure 4: As in Fig. 2 but adopting the S-5p TROPOMI corrected data.

Figure 5: As in Fig. 3 but adopting the S-5p TROPOMI corrected data.

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6. Conclusions

Here we report the primary outcomes of the analysis of possible benefits from correcting the S-5p TROPOMI NO₂ VCD with the SPC MAX-DOAS retrieved NO₂ tropospheric VCDs as a-priori NO₂ profiles. The assessment was performed evaluating the agreement of SPC MAX-DOAS retrieved NO₂ tropospheric VCDs with S-5p TROPOMI coincident data when applying or not the correction for the a-priori NO₂ profiles. For the correction, we used the profiles we retrieved from SPC MAX-DOAS measurements averaged in a time interval of +/- 15 minutes from S-5p TROPOMI overpasses. Only profiles that do not have negative values at any altitude level are used.

The impact of the correction goes in the same direction as highlighted in [R3]. The bias of TROPOMI-Skyspec-2D NO₂ Tropospheric VCDs moves from slightly negative (on average $-9 \cdot 10^{+14}$ mol/cm²) to slightly positive (on average $2.7 \cdot 10^{+14}$ mol/cm²) with a slope that increases from 0.69 to 0.77. As expected, the correction has the effect of enhancing the NO₂ TROPOMI VCDs.

7. References

[R1] van Geffen, J., Boersma, K. F., Eskes, H., Sneep, M., ter Linden, M., Zara, M., and Veefkind, J. P.: S5P TROPOMI NO₂ slant column retrieval: method, stability, uncertainties and comparisons with OMI, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 13, 1315–1335, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-13-1315-2020>, 2020.

[R2] Williams, J. E., Boersma, K. F., Le Sager, P., and Verstraeten, W. W.: The high-resolution version of TM5-MP for optimized satellite retrievals: description and validation, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 10, 721–750, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-10-721-2017>, 2017.

[R3] Dimitropoulou, E. and Hendrick, F. and Pinardi, G. and Friedrich, M. M. and Merlaud, A. and Tack, F. and De Longueville, H. and Fayt, C. and Hermans, C. and Laffineur, Q. and Fierens, F. and Van Roozendaal, M., Validation of TROPOMI tropospheric NO₂ columns using dual-scan multi-axis differential optical absorption spectroscopy (MAX-DOAS) measurements in Uccle, Brussels, *Atm. Meas. Tech.* 13, 2020, <https://amt.copernicus.org/articles/13/5165/2020/>.

[R4] Eskes, H., Jos van Geffen, Folkert Boersma, Kai-Uwe Eichmann, Arnoud Apituley, Mattia Pedernana, Maarten Sneep, J. Pepijn Veefkind, and Diego Loyola, Sentinel-5 precursor/TROPOMI Level 2 Product User Manual Nitrogen dioxide, S5P-KNMI-L2-0021-MA, issue 4.1.0, 2022/07/11.

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[R5] E. Castelli, P. Pettinari, E. Papandrea, M.Premuda, L. Di Liberto, M. Valeri [D-2] Report on the description of the MAX-DOAS profiles retrieval code and its validation, Report of WPs 2250-2251: “DOAS-BO: Towards a new FRM4DOAS-compliant site - Phase 2”, 2 December 2022.

[R6] Valeri, M. E. Castelli, P. Pettinari, E. Papandrea, L. Di Liberto, A. Marinoni, S. Decesari, [D-3] Report on the inter-comparison results between ground-based and satellite measurements, Report of WPs 2250-2251: “DOAS-BO: Towards a new FRM4DOAS-compliant site - Phase 2”, May 2023.